

THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND READING PROBLEMS IN THE NIGERIAN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract

This paper examines the role of English Language in solving reading problems in the Nigerian educational system for a sustainable development in a changing world. Being able to read well is crucially important for language learners. Successful performance at academic education is partly dependent on the ability to read. It is believed that good learners are those who are proficient in reading. However, building such a connection between a reader and the written information is complex and requires the application of various reading strategies. This paper therefore discusses the indispensability of reading, the place and importance of the English language in Nigerian education system, essential skills for reading, common reading problems, strategies for solving the reading problems and possible recommendations.

1. Introduction

Reading is a hallmark of literacy in any language. It is the keelson upon which micro and macro developments in different spheres of human pursuit are measured. Literacy has been and would continue to be an important requisite skill-set in determining individual's social status. In the words of Armstrong (2003) from ancient civilization to the present time, the balance of power resided in people who were literate. Literacy is the concern of so many disciplines, nations and organizations. This concern at the level of academic disciplines has given rise to what is now referred to as academic literacies, multiliteracies, new literacies or multimodal literacies (Kucer, 2014).

Reading can be silent (in our head) or aloud (so that other people can hear). Reading is a receptive skill-through it we receive information. But the complex process of reading also requires the skill of speaking so that we can pronounce the words that we read. In this sense, reading is also a productive skill in that we are both receiving information and transmitting it (even if only to ourselves). Reading is one of the four language skills, which are: Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing. Do we need to read in

order to speak English? The short answer is 'no'. Some native speakers cannot read or write but they speak English fluently. On the other hand, reading is something that one can do on his or her own and that greatly broadens one's vocabulary, thus helping in speaking (and in listening and writing). Reading is therefore a highly valuable skill and activity and it is recommended that English learners try to read as much as possible in English.

English language occupies a viable position in Nigeria because it is the single most important language, as her *lingua franca*, the language of law, legislative, administration and education. In the Nigerian educational system, English is the most important subject in the primary and secondary school curricula. As such, high performance in the language denoting adequate proficiency is the concern of every stakeholder in education (Banjo, 1996; Olaofe, 1997 and Bamgbose, 2000). The relevance of English language in Nigeria is therefore seen in education. English language is the medium of instruction virtually in all levels of Nigerian education system right from nursery to tertiary levels. This in spite of the provisions of the NPE (2004) which prescribes the use of Nigerian languages; the Mother Tongue (MT) or Language of Immediate Community (LIC) for instructions in nursery and lower primary school (Primary 1-3) (Fafunwa, 1998; Emenanjo, 2000). This has not still diminished the use of preference for English medium (Bodunde, 2004).

Since English is still being used as medium of instruction, this paper therefore seeks to explore the role of English language education in solving reading problems in the Nigerian educational system and also for a sustainable development in a changing world.

2. The Indispensability of Reading

The concept of reading encompasses a broad spectrum of activities. To read is to learn and grow, to experience, to understand, to marvel, to wonder, to laugh and the likes. Reading has been defined in so many ways by scholars, all gearing towards similar ideas. Reading is the interpretation of printed or written symbols into speech or its mental equivalent. There is no doubt that the graphic symbols perceived by the eyes are a product of something. It therefore means that reading requires a subject matter and the mind has to be actively involved in the business of interpretation.

Reading implies a silent process of hearing and listening to the writer speak to you or talk to you. Reading has been defined as a uniquely human activity closely linked to mark-making and record-keeping abilities (Holderness, 2003). It is an activity characterized by the translation of symbols, or letters, into words and sentences that communicate information and mean something to the reader.

Nwoke (2002) states that:

Reading involves the development of mental skills. It is a mechanical process involving print recognition ... for a learner to show perfect understanding of what he records; he must be involved in the intellectual activity of evaluating and synthesizing.

Similarly, reading is described by Amodu (2013) as a deliberate and conscious act of engaging one's eyes on written material for the purposes of understanding, obtaining general information or pleasure. In similar vein, Aliyu (2010) conceived the term as a way of building up from what has been put down in the written form ... He continued by saying that it is a form of communication during which the contents, challenges and claims made by a writer are gone over by the reader who tries to capture the substance of the written material.

In consonance with the above definitions, reading involves a reader's ability to choose from the text cues, predict possible meanings, self-connect where necessary and integrate the meaning gained from the text with the existing knowledge and understanding. Hence, it consists of two processes- visual and mental or intellectual process. Thus, reading is the process of looking at a series of written symbols and getting meaning from them.

The place of reading in all spheres of our educational system, in our daily interaction with people, and materials cannot be over-emphasized. Reading plays fundamental roles, in fact, two many to be enumerated among which includes exposure to new ideas, things and places, self-improvement, enhancing understanding and comprehension, an important tool for communicating with others and above all, a strong weapon of creativity and imagination. As Andre Mairois (2017) observes;

The art of reading is in great part that of acquiring a better understanding of life from one's encounter with it in a book.

Books play a fundamental role in our lives. There is a profound statement about books that merits our attention that "**when you open a book, you open a new world**". This statement cannot be dismissed by many since there is a symbiotic relationship between books and mankind. Man has formed an intricate partnership with books since the advent of writing culminating in documenting our past histories, cultures, traditions, inventions and ideas that have formed part of our contemporary existence. The role of books and reading is globally recognized as the world celebrates, **World Book Day on the 23rd of April, every year**. The day also marks the recognition of writers, illustrators and importantly, reading. The significance of this day is aptly described in these words.

The reason for choosing this particular date is interesting. The 23rd of April is a symbolic date for world literature because it is the date of death for many great authors and poets such as William Shakespeare, Miguel de Cervantes. William Wordsworth and many others (<http://max.se//thoughts/theimportantofbooksinourlife>).

The publication of books provide the reading public an opportunity to arm themselves with information, skills, knowledge and, power. Victoria (2017) affirms this role when she states that a book communicates knowledge, and not only knowledge but wisdom of all kinds. They say that "the more you read, the more well read you are. In simple terms what this means is that, the more you read, the more exposed you are; your attitudes, ideas and imagination changes". Many experts have also attested to the indispensable role of reading in our lives, society and future survival. According to Enrikson (2017):

There is an old saying, "the pen is mightier than the sword". Ideas written down have changed the destiny of men and nations for better or for worse. The flow of ideas cannot be stopped. We need to read and research to build on the good ideas and expose the bad ideas before they bring destruction. Only by reading can we be armed in this never ending life and death struggle.

With reading comes literacy. A literate people cannot be naive, manipulated by those in authority. They know where their rights lie and they struggle to pursue and get them. It is in view of this fact that Enrikson (2017) states that:

The fact of the power of the written ideas communicated through reading is a fundamental reason why some governments oppose free and honest communication. Illiterate people are easier to control and manipulated. They cannot do their research and thinking, they must rely on what they are told and how their emotions are swayed.

Besides, according to Jenkins (2011), people who read books regularly are on the average are more satisfied with life, happier and more likely to feel that the things they do in life are worthwhile. In fact, the importance of reading are inexhaustible.

On the other hand, the neglect of reading has grievous impact in the overall educational process and attainment. According to Omo-Ojugo (2005) cited in Ifedi (2007):

The World Bank in conjunction with Nigeria Institute of Social and Economic Research, Ibadan produced a grim report in the Nigerian graduate which has confirmed the fears of educators, parents, employers and the general public about the degeneration of the country's education. The report revealed that the average graduates who leave university or a polytechnic with a degree or certificate is not worth the qualification, which he is supposed to

have. The report concluded by saying that the average Nigerian graduate lacks technical skills, has a poor command of English... and largely unemployable. Harold stated that lack of vibrant reading culture has been a publishers' nightmare. The government effort in fighting illiteracy is being thwarted by students who do not read neither their prescribed textbooks nor for pleasure.

Few global reports emanating from researches and surveys will suffice here:

- a. Low level of literacy cost the United Kingdom an estimated 8 billion (pounds) a year in lost earnings, and increased welfare spending impacting on the success of the economy as a whole.
- b. Adults with low levels of literacy are more likely to experience poor health and to believe that they have little impact on political processes and are less likely to participate in volunteer activities.
- c. Literacy has been found to have a relationship with depression. 36% of those with low literacy were found to have depressive symptoms, compared to 20% of those with highest levels of literacy.

3. Types of Reading Techniques

i. Skimming:

Skimming sometimes referred to as gist reading, meaning going through the text to grasp the main idea. Here, the reader doesn't pronounce each and every word of the text but focuses their attention on the main theme or the core of the text. Examples of skimming are reading magazines or newspapers and searching for a name in a telephone directory.

ii. Scanning:

Here, the reader quickly scuttles across sentences to get a particular piece of information. Scanning involves the techniques of rejecting or ignoring irrelevant information from the text to locate a specific piece of information.

iii. Intensive Reading:

Intensive reading is far more time consuming than skimming and scanning as it needs the reader's attention. It involves close reading that aims at the accuracy of comprehension. Here, the reader has to understand the meaning of each and every word.

iv. Extensive Reading:

Extensive reading lays more emphasis on fluency and less on accuracy. It usually involves reading for pleasure and is more of an out-of-classroom activity. It is highly unlikely for readers to take up the extensive reading of text they do not like.

4. Importance of Reading

i. Reading Reduces Stress:

Reading has also been identified as a reliable method of reducing stress. For example, a 2009 study completed by the University of Sussex reported that reading a book worked better and faster than going for a walk, listening to music and drinking a cup of tea. In fact, it reduces stress up to 60 percent.

ii. Reading Stimulates the Brain:

Reading is a great mental stimulation exercise that keeps the brain busy so it would preserve its mental power. Like a muscle, the brain needs to stay fit and strong to be able to function properly. So, reading becomes an intense workout for it. A 2013 study that appeared in Neurology journal found out that reading books can help to keep memory and thinking skills intact.

iii. Reading Improves Memory:

Every new memory created by the brain improves short term memory by generating new synapses and strengthening new ones.

iv. Reading Helps to Appreciate Art and Engage in Social Work:

According to the National Endowment for the Arts and other organizations, people who read a lot are several times more likely to visit concerts and museums than those who do not. Thus, book reading encourages people to actively participate in the social work and improve the world around them.

v. Reading Improves Analytic Thinking Skills:

Analytic thinking is an essential skill for many professions. Reading is an effective tool for improving it. For example, have one ever read a book and guessed the ending correctly before he or she finished it? If one has, it might be a proof that one's analytical skills are good.

5. Essential Skills for Reading Success

i. Decoding

Decoding is the ability to sound out words one has heard before but hasn't seen it written out. This is a vital step in the reading process as it forms the foundation for other reading skills. Decoding heavily relies on an early language skill called phonemic awareness. Phonemic awareness is the ability to hear

and manipulate different sounds into words. One develops this awareness when learning about syllables, words and sounds (phonemes).

ii. Phonics

Phonics is the ability to recognize the connection between sounds and letters they make. This process of mapping the sounds in words to written words is a very important reading skill. One first decodes into sounds and encodes the sound into words as he or she writes and spells.

iii. Vocabulary

A good vocabulary is a fundamental part of academic success. This reading skill is necessary to understanding the meaning of words, their definitions, and their context. The more words we know, the better our reading and understanding of the texts read.

iv. Fluency

Fluency is the ability to read aloud with understanding, accuracy and speed. It is a skill needed for good reading comprehension. Individuals fluent in reading know how to read smoothly at a good pace using proper time and without making too many errors.

v. Sentence Construction and Cohesion

Sentence construction and cohesion may seem like a writing skill. It's an essential reading skill. Connecting ideas between and within the sentences are called cohesion, and these skills are essential for reading comprehension.

vi. Reading Comprehension

It has to do with understanding the meaning of texts both in story books and information books. In fiction books, one imagines the characters and share an emotional and adventurous journey with them. In non-fiction books, individuals gain new information which deepens their understanding of new topics and concepts. Reading comprehension is a complex skill that requires time and practice to develop fully.

vii. Reasoning and Background Knowledge

This skill helps one use the background knowledge to make inferences and draw conclusions. Most readers can relate what they have read to what they know. They can also read between lines to pull out the information when it's not literally spelled out in the text.

viii. Working Memory and Attention

These skills are closely related but different and are part of a group of abilities known as executive function. When individuals read, attention helps them absorb the information from the text and working

memory allows them to retain that information. This helps them gain meaning and build knowledge from what they read.

6. Common Reading Problems

i. Issues with Decoding

Beginner readers may struggle when they meet new or unfamiliar terms, but typically decoding becomes easier with repeated practice of reading the text out loud. If one continues to struggle, there may be an underlying difficulty or a physical impairment that does not allow them to hear the sounds or see the letters.

ii. Poor Comprehension of Reading Skills

Some individuals read like a pro but may not be able to tell you what they have read. This indicates a problem of comprehension. They may find the same difficulty when other readers read aloud.

iii. Speed

The more one reads, the more he or she expands in vocabulary. He or she begins to recognize more words by sight, enabling him or her to read faster. If speed is the issue, slow processing of information could be the problem. Since reading is a cognitively demanding task, it involves holding information in the mind while continuously processing the text. This can exhaust readers with slow processing. Such readers may require extra time to complete tasks that require extensive reading.

iv. Mixed Reading Difficulties

Mixed reading problems in some readers include; decoding words and difficulty with comprehension. They have challenges when it comes to reading words, retaining information and understanding the text. These problems could be due to a reading disorder though some individuals learn slower than others.

7. The Place and Importance of English Language in the Education System

Language is the first medium used by people to share their thoughts and information with other people. There are a lot of languages people can speak around the world. People who belong to different places and regions speak their own languages. Most countries and regions have their own national language and their people can speak other different languages.

Language allows people to develop a sense of self and to interact with others in the community. Language is the means through which knowledge is transmitted. Every form of education, formal, informal or non-formal is expressed and acquired through language. Through education, a man's

potentials are developed; skills, knowledge and expertise that will enable man become more productive and creative in his environment are acquired. Through education, man is equipped to engage in profitable ventures that would earn him higher income and improve his standard of living. Man is enabled to gain access to better health care and other social services that add value to his or her life. Thus, education is regarded as a powerful instrument for human development.

However, the issue of education cannot be discussed without language through which the concepts are expressed. Because no matter how expertly the learning experiences are selected and organized, the ultimate objective of teaching-learning exercise would not be achieved if language of instruction is unfamiliar to the learner. English language is the language of education in Nigeria. It is the language of instruction from upper primary education through secondary and tertiary educations in Nigeria. A good knowledge of the socio-political history of Nigeria will enable one understand how English language came into Nigeria and occupied a colossal position in the Nigerian education system. Nigeria is made up of multilingual and multiethnic nationals wielded together for the benefit of the colonial administration. After independence, the Nigerian system of education did not change much from what it was during the colonial era.

English language remained the pivot of education in Nigeria. it is the language through which all other subjects in the curriculum are taught. Not only is English language a compulsory subject in secondary school, a credit pass in it is a compulsory condition for securing admission into Nigerian tertiary institutions. Competence in English is seen as an index of academic excellence. Thus, it is a yardstick for measuring learner's academic performance. More so, before any student can graduate from the tertiary institutions in Nigeria, they must pass the course "Use of English".

English language is the bedrock upon which education in Nigeria is hinged. Suffice it then to say that English is indispensable to education in Nigeria. The state of English as a second language in Nigeria coupled with the numerous roles it plays compels every Nigerian citizen to learn and to speak it. This paper therefore submits that if English language is the medium through which the concepts in education are expressed and acquired, then it is a primary instrument for human and sustainable development in Nigeria. English language has not only engineered human and sustainable development through education, it has also conferred in Nigerians other significant privileges both in the home front and the global scene.

Based on this backdrop, this paper explores the role of English language education in solving reading problems in the Nigerian educational system for sustainable development in a changing world.

8. The Role of English Language in Solving Reading Problems

English language plays an essential role in our lives as it helps in communication. It is the main language for studying any subject all over the world. English is important to students as it broadens their minds, develops emotional skills and improves their quality of life. English language is a vital and compulsory subject in the Nigerian educational system. English language plays a vital role and goes a long way in solving reading problems.

Literacy teaching and learning are core responsibilities of teachers and schools. Yet teaching reading is a complex and highly skilled professional activity. Many young learners start school with little knowledge about how to read. Teachers are tasked with helping children to bridge the significant gap between linking their written and spoken language. Learning to read is critical with research showing that reading for pleasure can:

- i. Promote improved health and wellbeing.
- ii. Help build social connections and relationships.
- iii. Increase the chances of social mobility.

Literacy development is an evolving and non-linear process that encompasses foundational skills (phonemic awareness), word recognition, reading fluency, vocabulary and reading comprehension (Simms and Marzano, 2018). Comprehension is not something that happens automatically in the mind of the reader as he or she engages with print, even though it may seem that way to adult proficient readers. Reading comprehension is an active, thoughtful, strategic and multidimensional process that readers employ to take in new meaning from the written text and fit (or file) it into their existing knowledge structures (files). It is the job of teachers to help students become aware of, or acquire, and employ this process in their own reading.

Teaching a student to read especially in English language is arguably one of the most important functions of the teaching profession. The ability to read, and read for comprehension, opens up an entire world of possibilities and opportunities for children to discover new worlds and learn new concepts. And while teaching reading via English language is such a high priority, some teachers who are not specially trained in the practice find themselves seeking additional help. The good news is that there are many instructional strategies to solving reading problems via English language that nearly any educator can implement. Before anyone can effectively teach or solve reading problems, it is vital that one understands the primary components of reading instruction. When broken down into five major elements, reading

instruction is a much more approachable and easily understood skill. The five (5) elements of reading instructions are:

- i. Phonics:** This has to do with the relationship between letters and the different sounds they make. This can be in relation to single letters or grouping of letters.
- ii. Phonemic Awareness:** This is an understanding of how consonant or vowel sounds can be arranged to make words. Examples of phonemic awareness include being able to identify words that rhyme, recognizing alliteration, segmenting a sentence into words, identifying the syllabus in a word, and blending and segmenting onsets.
- iii. Vocabulary:** This has to do with the range of words a student is able to understand and use in context.
- iv. Fluency:** This is the ability to read and understand words with accuracy, speed and comprehension.
- v. Comprehension:** This is the complete understanding of information being delivered by a text.

The following are strategies via English language to solving reading problems;

i. Assessing student ability first

Beginning by getting a baseline reading of each student's current reading level, this will help to:

- a. understand the abilities that one is working with and how to group students (which is another effective instructional strategy) and
- b. determine what reading strategies and tools will work best for each student's individual needs.

ii. Choral reading/Partner reading

Choral reading is an exercise where the teacher and class read a text aloud together in unison. This allows struggling readers to still participate in the practice of reading without embarrassment, and it has been shown to improve fluency and confidence. Partner reading is a small version of choral reading, where students are grouped together to read a text aloud with a partner, alternating sentences or paragraphs.

iii. Using of visual aids

This practice is aimed at improving students' reading comprehension more than their actual reading ability, but comprehension is a key element in overall reading skill. Many educators find that using visual tools like graphic organizers to help students break down the text they are reading helps make it more digestible and easily understood. These can be completed individually or in a group brainstorm session, which helps readers see different perspectives and deepen their comprehension.

iv. Assigning reading buddies across ages and grades

This is like a mentorship programme, where older students with demonstrable reading abilities are paired up with younger, new readers to help them improve. Younger readers get to see high-level reading modeled by the older students, and the older students learn the valuable skills of mentorship, patience and how to give direction. What's more, if there are older students who are struggling with reading at their grade level, a reading buddy programme would allow them to be exposed to more approachable reading materials with the younger students, only helping to build their confidence and ability.

v. Implementing audio-books

Using audio-books while reading also known as ear reading – is a great way to assist struggling readers. While this shouldn't be the primary practice, using audio-books in conjunction with focused phonics instruction has been proven to help students improve their reading accuracy. And that benefit applies to students across all abilities and skill levels.

vi. Teaching academic English

To teach academic English means teaching general and domain-specific vocabulary in accordance with a subject or unit. While vocabulary is sometimes thought of as separate from reading instruction, it is actually an integral part in improving reading abilities. This has been a proven tactic, but these practices help readers of all levels and backgrounds.

vii. Having students summarize what they read

As a quick comprehension check, students can be asked to write a brief paragraph summary of what they just read, immediately after they complete the reading task. Writing summaries help them to breakdown large concepts, focus on the most important details and retain what they read. If a whole paragraph is too much for some students, getting a simple who, what, when, where, why and how explanation is an equally effective tactic.

viii. Exposing students to different discourse patterns

Most academic reading is in the form of narrative discourse, and it is what most students are familiar and comfortable with. To help expose them to different types of text and diversify their skills, introduce alternative discourse patterns in the form of an article or a personal letter. These are comprehension abilities they will need to have and will support their ability to read and understand narrative writing as well.

ix. Allowing students choose the books they read

Students are much more likely to be excited to read when they get the opportunity to read about something they are interested in. Curating a short list of options for students and letting them pick – this will improve their engagement and create enthusiasm about reading.

x. Making students read the same content multiple times

As it is said, that practice makes perfect and that rings true for reading tool. This practice was formally known as Fluency-Oriented Reading Instruction (FORI) and calls for students to read the same text multiple times in different settings – silently, out loud, in pairs, in groups, solo and so on. This helps students improve their pronunciation and comprehension and solidifies the skills they are learning in individualized reading instruction.

9. Conclusion

Opportunities for teaching and solving reading problems occur at all levels throughout the curriculum. Good comprehension draws from both linguistic knowledge and knowledge of the world we live in. Students develop skills in comprehension through high-quality discussion with teachers, and from regularly reading and discussing a range of texts across genres. Therefore, the reading strategies for solving reading problems discussed in this paper should be practiced, consolidated and expanded on as the students' progress through school.

Growing readers must learn to read on the lines, between the lines, and beyond the lines. Reading will involve literal, interpretive and inferential comprehension as it deepens in complexity. As students get more advanced, they will learn concepts such as transferring knowledge to contexts and understanding an author's view point, purpose and intended audience. When they acquire those skills, they will be able to critically analyze messages and information in a range of literacy modes for various purposes.

10. Recommendations

- i. Students should spend significant amounts of time reading engaging text.
- ii. Teachers should select texts for students which support authentic learning. These could include topic-based or interest-based texts.
- iii. Teachers should give students access to a range of texts in various genres (multimodal, print-based, images, animations, graphic representations, video, audio, diagrams/charts, news-papers/magazines, fiction and non-fiction).
- iv. Teachers should give the students time to talk to each other about the text they have read and listened to.

v. Students should be given time to write and reflect on their reading.

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